

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW PROTOCOL FOR ANIMAL INTERVENTION STUDIES

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Item #	Section/Subsection/Item	Description	Check for approval
A. General			
1.	Title of the review	Osteoblast-osteoclast co-culture models of bone-remodelling: A systematic review.	
2.	Authors (names, affiliations, contributions)	<p>Stefan Remmers¹, Bregje de Wildt¹, Michelle Vis¹, Rob de Vries², Keita Ito^{1,3}, Sandra Hofmann¹</p> <p>¹Orthopaedic Biomechanics, Department of Biomedical Engineering and the Institute for Complex Molecular Systems, Eindhoven University of Technology, Eindhoven, The Netherlands</p> <p>²SYRCLE, Department for Health Evidence, Radboud Institute for Health Sciences, Radboudumc, Nijmegen, The Netherlands</p> <p>³Department of Orthopaedics, UMC Utrecht, Utrecht, The Netherlands</p>	
3.	Other contributors (names, affiliations, contributions)		
4.	Contact person + e-mail address	Stefan Remmers, s.j.a.remmers@tue.nl	
5.	Funding sources/sponsors	European Union's Seventh Framework Programme (FP/2007-2013) / EU Project No. 336043	
6.	Conflicts of interest		
7.	Date and location of protocol registration		
8.	Registration number (if applicable)		
9.	Stage of review at time of registration	Selection stage	
B. Objectives			
Background			
10.	What is already known about this disease/model/intervention? Why is it important to do this review?	<p>Animal studies are morally problematic, expensive, time consuming and often not accurate or not suitable for translation to humans. Adaptation of suitable <i>in vitro</i> models could provide an additional tool of selection prior to animal experiments, effectively reducing the number of experiments and the number of experimental groups needed. Many groups, including our own, have recently attempted to develop an <i>in vitro</i> model of bone remodelling. Osteoblasts (bone forming cells) have been studied extensively and can be used reliably to show mineral deposition. The addition of osteoclasts (bone resorbing cells) often proves difficult, especially if quantifiable outcome measures are desired. All groups work on their own model system, and all use different methodologies and cell-culture conditions. Culture conditions and analyses vary widely and are not standardized. The goal of this systematic review is</p>	

		therefore to identify all relevant co-culture studies of osteoblast- and osteoclast-like cells, in order to determine which methods result in quantifiable outcomes and facilitate the use of quantifiable outcome measures to measure bone formation and resorption, with the aim of developing a standard for co-culture models of bone-remodelling.	
Research question			
11.	Specify the disease/health problem of interest	The co-culture models can be used for fundamental research on bone remodelling, studying bone diseases such as osteoporosis, drug development, and personalized medicine.	
12.	Specify the population/species studied	Co-cultures of either human or animal primary cells or cell lines that contain both osteoblasts and osteoclasts	
13.	Specify the intervention/exposure	The cell-culture model exposed to plain osteoblastic and / or osteoclastic culture medium, supplemented with any kind of biochemical variation, or exposed to mechanical loading.	
14.	Specify the control population	The cell-culture model exposed to plain osteoblastic and / or osteoclastic culture medium	
15.	Specify the outcome measures	Measured osteoblast activity or bone formation (mineralization / calcium deposition), and measured osteoclast activity or bone resorption.	
16.	State your research question (based on items 11-15)	Main question: Which are the current osteoblast-osteoclast co-culture models? Subquestions: - Which of those have quantifiable outcome measures on bone formation or resorption? - What methodological approaches and experimental conditions facilitate simultaneously studying changes in resorption and formation best?	
C. Methods			
Search and study identification			
17.	Identify literature databases to search (e.g. Pubmed, Embase, Web of science)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> MEDLINE via PubMed <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Web of Science <input type="checkbox"/> SCOPUS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EMBASE <input type="checkbox"/> Other, namely: <input type="checkbox"/> Specific journal(s), namely:	
18.	Define electronic search strategies (e.g. use the step by step search guide ¹⁵ and animal search filters ^{20, 21})	When available, please add a supplementary file containing your search strategy: [insert file name]	
19.	Identify other sources for study identification	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reference lists of included studies <input type="checkbox"/> Books <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reference lists of relevant reviews <input type="checkbox"/> Conference proceedings, namely: <input type="checkbox"/> Contacting authors/ organisations, namely: <input type="checkbox"/> Other, namely:	
20.	Define search strategy for these other sources	Of all studies included after the final screening phase and all related reviews, the titles in the reference lists will be	

		screened for additional includable studies. If from the title is seems likely that a study could match the criteria, it is added to a list of new studies, that are screened in the same way as the originally included studies.	
Study selection			
21.	Define screening phases (<i>e.g.</i> pre-screening based on title/abstract, full text screening, both)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phase 1: Pre-screening based on title/abstract for bone-related co-culture primary studies • Phase 2: full-text screening. In case of doubt in phase 1, screen full text for bone-related co-cultures. • Phase 3 (within review): full-text screening for relevant outcome measures • Phase 4 (within review): full-text screening for applicability as a model for bone remodeling 	
22.	Specify (a) the number of reviewers per screening phase and (b) how discrepancies will be resolved	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. 2 reviewers will independently screen titles, abstracts and full texts. b. If the reviewers disagree, they will discuss together. If no consensus can be reached, a 3rd reviewer will be consulted. 	
<i>Define all inclusion and exclusion criteria based on:</i>			
23.	Type of study (design)	<p>Inclusion criteria: experiment is a primary study</p> <p>Exclusion criteria: not a primary study. Reviews on the subject (will be used as an additional source to locate studies), conference abstracts</p>	
24.	Type of animals/population (<i>e.g.</i> age, gender, disease model)	<p>Inclusion criteria: Study uses osteoblastic and osteoclastic cells, or cell lines and/or progenitor cells of those cells, as long as they are expected to differentiate into the required cell types. A heterogeneous cell mix is allowed if it is related to the osteoblastic or osteoclastic lineages, and the fraction of necessary precursors of finally differentiated cells is measured.(<i>e.g.</i> blood derived mononuclear cells, mesenchymal stromal cells) The addition of a 3rd or 4th cell type is permitted, as long as the aforementioned 2 are present as well. Source may be human or any animal. Study is bone related.</p> <p>Exclusion criteria: Does not contain osteoblasts AND osteoclasts, or related/progenitor cells. Study is not bone related.</p>	
25.	Type of intervention (<i>e.g.</i> dosage, timing, frequency)	Intervention is not part of initial inclusion or exclusion criteria	
26.	Outcome measures	<p>Inclusion criteria: Any outcome related to bone formation or resorption</p> <p>Exclusion criteria: No bone-related outcome</p>	
27.	Language restrictions	<p>Inclusion criteria: No restrictions</p> <p>Exclusion criteria: None</p>	
28.	Publication date restrictions	<p>Inclusion criteria: No restrictions</p> <p>Exclusion criteria: None</p>	
29.	Other	<p>Inclusion criteria: All unique studies</p> <p>Exclusion criteria: If deemed necessary, the same</p>	

		experiment lead to different publications. These publications will not be excluded, but if discovered will be grouped and treated as one large study. In a similar way, recurring methods by the same group will be treated as one.	
30.	Sort and prioritize your exclusion criteria per selection phase	<p>Selection phase 1 (tiab):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not both osteoblasts and osteoclasts - No in vitro study - Not a primary study - Not bone related <p>Selection phase 2 (full text):</p> <p>Same as in phase 1 for those studies where title/abstract was not sufficient. The result of this is a comprehensive list of all osteoblast-osteoclast co-cultures.</p> <p>Phase 3 (outcome measures; within review):</p> <p>Within these results, all included studies will be further assessed on investigating the desired outcome measures using full text screening. Inclusion criteria in order of importance are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Resorption as outcome measure -Formation as outcome measure -Quantified osteoblast (ALP) or osteoclast (TRAP) activity <p>Studies with other outcome measures or interesting methods that could be of interest are included on a separate list as well.</p> <p>Phase 4 (applicability to study bone remodeling): Each study included in phase 3 is characterized based on the ability to serve as a co-culture model using the following categories; 'Only osteoclasts are studied', 'Only osteoblasts are studied', 'Both osteoblasts and osteoclasts are studied'. Studies where only one cell type is studied will be placed on a separate list.</p> <p>All studies placed on separate lists are used to extract information on their methods and outcome measures only. All studies in the main dataset where both celltypes are studied AND at least resorption, formation or cell activity is measured will be used completely.</p>	
Study characteristics to be extracted (for assessment of external validity, reporting quality)			
31.	Study ID (e.g. authors, year)	Authors, year	
32.	Study design characteristics (e.g. experimental groups, number of animals)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Type of co-culture 2. Experimental / intervention groups 3. Timeline of experiment 4. Sample size 	
33.	Animal model characteristics (e.g. species, gender, disease induction)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Type of osteoblastic cells 2. Type of osteoclastic cells 3. Cell-culture details: seeding density, moment of 	

		seeding, medium compositions	
34.	Intervention characteristics (<i>e.g.</i> intervention, timing, duration)	Intervention, concentration, duration, timing	
35.	Outcome measures	Method of measuring bone formation/resorption, with a special interest in any quantifiable osteoblast activity, mineral deposition or bone formation, and quantifiable osteoclast activity or bone resorption.	
36.	Other (<i>e.g.</i> drop-outs)	Sample dropout rate, if available	
Assessment risk of bias (internal validity) or study quality			
37.	Specify (a) the number of reviewers assessing the risk of bias/study quality in each study and (b) how discrepancies will be resolved	<p>a. 2</p> <p>b. 2 reviewers will independently assess the risk of bias/study quality of each study. If the reviewers disagree, they will discuss together. If no consensus can be reached, a 3th reviewer will be consulted.</p>	
38.	Define criteria to assess (a) the internal validity of included studies (<i>e.g.</i> selection, performance, detection and attrition bias) and/or (b) other study quality measures (<i>e.g.</i> reporting quality, power)	<p><input type="checkbox"/> By use of SYRCLE's Risk of Bias tool</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> By use of SYRCLE's Risk of Bias tool, adapted as follows:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> By use of CAMARADES' study quality checklist, e.g ²²</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> By use of CAMARADES' study quality checklist, adapted as follows:</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other criteria, namely: adapted version of the OHAT/NTP in vitro risk of bias tool + reporting of sample size calculation</p>	
Collection of outcome data			
39.	For each outcome measure, define the type of data to be extracted (<i>e.g.</i> continuous/dichotomous, unit of measurement)	<p>Bone formation (expressed as <i>e.g.</i> volume, surface area, percentage, relative gene expression, protein release, enzyme activity). - continuous</p> <p>Bone resorption (expressed as <i>e.g.</i> volume, surface area, percentage, relative gene expression, protein release, enzyme activity) - continuous</p>	
40.	Methods for data extraction/retrieval (<i>e.g.</i> first extraction from graphs using a digital screen ruler, then contacting authors)	First from text, then from graph, finally from authors.	
41.	Specify (a) the number of reviewers extracting data and (b) how discrepancies will be resolved	<p>a. 2 reviewers will independently extract the data from the papers</p> <p>b. If the reviewers disagree, they will discuss together. If no consensus can be reached, a 3th reviewer will be consulted.</p>	
Data analysis/synthesis			
42.	Specify (per outcome measure) how you are planning to combine/compare the data (<i>e.g.</i> descriptive summary, meta-analysis)	Descriptive summary of results (statistically significant change in bone formation/resorption or not), while comparing different (co-)culture conditions	
43.	Specify (per outcome measure) how it will be decided whether a meta-analysis will be performed	As we do not want to compare the effect sizes between different studies, a meta-analysis is not useful.	
<i>If a meta-analysis seems feasible/sensible, specify (for each outcome measure):</i>			

44.	The effect measure to be used (<i>e.g.</i> mean difference, standardized mean difference, risk ratio, odds ratio)	-	
45.	The statistical model of analysis (<i>e.g.</i> random or fixed effects model)	-	
46.	The statistical methods to assess heterogeneity (<i>e.g.</i> I^2 , Q)	-	
47.	Which study characteristics will be examined as potential source of heterogeneity (subgroup analysis)	-	
48.	Any sensitivity analyses you propose to perform	-	
49.	Other details meta-analysis (<i>e.g.</i> correction for multiple testing, correction for multiple use of control group)	-	
50.	The method for assessment of publication bias	-	

Final approval by (names, affiliations):		Date:
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